

Appendix 1 — Structured Observation Data: All Four Observer Sheets

This appendix presents the complete observation data from all four observer sheets in a single structured table, organised by team and phase. Observer scores are presented side-by-side to enable comparison. The lead observer for each team used the wall clock in the room; all timing is taken from lead observer records only. Qualitative notes and direct quotes are reproduced verbatim from the observation sheets. Student names have been withheld. Where two observers recorded the same team, their scores are listed separately as Lead and Second observer.

A. Session Details

Detail	Team 1 (Against the motion)	Team 2 (For the motion)
Date	31 March 2026	31 March 2026
Age range	13–15 years	12–13 years
Number of students	6	6
Lead observer	Lead researcher	Lead researcher (wall clock used for all timing)
Second observer	Second observer	Second observer
Debate start time	2:05 p.m.	2:03 p.m. (5 mins prep; debate began 2:05 p.m.)
Switch time	Not recorded by lead observer	2:23 p.m.
Total session duration	35 minutes	32 minutes
Room setup	Two half-circles facing each other, well-ventilated room	Two semi-circles facing each other, open setting

B. Phase 1 — Scored Metrics (Before the Switch)

Metric (scale 1–5)	Team 1	Team 1	Team 2	Team 2
	Lead	Second	Lead	Second
Originality of arguments	5	3	2	3
Personal ownership of position	4	4	2	4
Use of lived experience as evidence	4	4	1	4
Willingness to speak unprompted	4	4	2	3
Responsiveness to opposing side	4	4	—	3

B2. Phase 1 — Notable Arguments and Qualitative Observations

	Team 1 (Against the motion)	Team 2 (For the motion)
Notable arguments (verbatim or paraphrased)	'If a 16-year-old chooses the wrong person who rules for five years and again as a cycle this happens, what happens to our country?' 'Natural unbiased brain' 'Voting is not a practice' 'We are not saying 18 is the right age either' 'How do you know propaganda is towards adults if kids are not even included?'	'Adults do not care' 'Preconceived notions take more precedence as they grow older' 'Adults are more money hungry than kids' 'Political propaganda targeted towards adults' 'More people will vote, influenced by social media; elder people may believe [false information]'
Unexpected observations	Exam pressure raised spontaneously as a constraint on 16-year-old voters (Lead observer)	Several students performing rather than owning position (Lead observer). 'Basically teenagers, mostly developed (not fully)' (Second observer)
Emotional register	Calm and passionate (Lead); No — passive (Second observer note: 'almost everyone involved actively')	Hesitant and playful (Lead); Passionate and hesitant (Second)

C. The Switch Moment

Observation	Team 1 (Against → For)	Team 2 (For → Against)
First observable reaction	Laughter / deflection	Silence / freeze and negotiation / clarification
Duration of disruption	~2 minutes	~10 seconds pause, then ~2 minutes to confer
Exact words at moment of switch	'They will just steal our points — should we do different points? They are not allowed to repeat our points, right?' (Lead observer) 'Should we do different points? / They are not allowed to repeat our points, right?' (Second observer)	'Who won the debate so far?' 'They shouldn't use the same arguments as we did' 'We can use but we shouldn't' 'Can we at least get 5 minutes?' (Lead observer) 'They can't say anything [from] what we spoke' (Second observer)
Resistance score (1–5, high = strong resistance)	Lead: 2 / Second: 2	Lead: 2 / Second: 3
Resistance observer notes	'First they hesitated but then switched sides nicely' (Second) 'Student: Can we do a different topic? Researcher: No. Student: Okay.' (Lead)	'Not much strong. Surprised at beginning but took it sportingly' (Lead) 'No resistance, just time to reconsider their points' (Second)
Cross-listening score (1–5)	Lead: 1 (tried to eavesdrop) / Second: 4	Lead: 3 / Second: 4
Who switched most smoothly	High-confidence speakers (Lead) / Even across group (Second)	Quieter students (Lead) / High-confidence speakers (Second)
Who resisted most strongly	High-confidence speakers (Lead) / No resistance (Second)	High-confidence speakers (Lead) / Even across group (Second)
Students silent after switch	A few remained silent (Second observer)	Some went silent but pitched in where required (Lead)

D. Phase 2 — Scored Metrics (After the Switch)

Metric (scale 1–5)	Team 1	Team 1	Team 2	Team 2
	Lead	Second	Lead	Second
Argumentation quality (vs Phase 1)	3	2	2	3
Intellectual flexibility	3	2	5	3
Use of Phase 1 material against self	4	3	4	3
Group cohesion after switch	5	4	4	2
Civic identity discomfort (1–5)	2	4	3	4

D2. Phase 2 — Notable Arguments and Civic Self-Positioning

	Team 1 (now arguing For)	Team 2 (now arguing Against)
Most striking argument after switch	'Society cages us as we grow older — at 16, not as much.' (Lead observer) '16-year-olds will have exam pressure' (Second observer)	'People become more mature from 16–18 and are influenced by society, so have more experience to vote for change.' (Lead observer) 'For 16-year-olds exam pressure is there but so is at 18, so why not start at 16? At 16 they are more at ease.' (Second observer)
Civic self-positioning quotes	'Immature' [used about own age group, visible discomfort noted] 'We are not caged by society as much as 18-year-olds'	'We can say that we aren't mature enough compared to adults, but we won't — because we are mature enough for that age.' (Second observer)
Group cohesion notes	Remained same; students helping each other find new arguments (Lead) Reformed quickly; thought as a group on what to speak (Second)	Remained intact, collaborative (Lead) Scattered; one student leading arguments both before and after switch (Second)
Peer dynamics	Students helping each other find new arguments (Lead)	Competitive — using switch to gain advantage (Second) Students helping each other find new arguments (Lead)

E–F. Cross-Study Observations and Researcher Synthesis

	Team 1	Team 2
Inquiry behaviours (Case 1 / Flipside)	Partially — interested in everyone's views even when competitive (Lead observer)	Not recorded
Resilience behaviours (Case 4 / Resilience Workshop)	Yes — adapted quickly to the change despite initial shock (Lead observer)	Not recorded
Lead researcher synthesis	'They had some trouble with the initial ownership but once they got into a rhythm they spoke with clarity. The disruption stunned them initially but they fought back with equal vigour.'	Not completed at time of data collection.
Second observer synthesis	Not completed at time of data collection.	'They weren't confident in defending the age to be reduced to 16, but they were defensive in asking why not. They haven't delved into what a 16-year-old will be voting for. They stuck on who gets lured easier than who gets to create change through voting in a democratic republic.'
What to do differently	'While they are young and vibrant, some of them need a bit more structure. We should nudge them a bit towards that structure.' (Lead observer)	'Prep some prompts to nudge them into right arguments and sensible points. Give them more time and ask them to wholly reflect on different angles. A briefing discussion — a heads-up — could have brought more great points.' (Second observer)
Overall session quality rating	Lead: 4 out of 5 / Second: not recorded	Lead: not recorded / Second: 3 out of 5

Table note: All scores are on a 1–5 scale as specified in the observation instrument. Direct quotes are reproduced verbatim from the observer sheets. Dashes and 'not recorded' indicate sections not completed by that observer. Student names have been withheld throughout. All timing is taken from lead observer records using the wall clock in the room.